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Kenneth MacMillan and the Subject Matter of Ballet

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ABSTRACT

Sex, violence, and visceral elements of similar dramatic tenor feature frequently in ballets by the British choreographer Kenneth MacMillan. Although he publicly acknowledged the decisive impact of John Osborne's play *Look Back in Anger* on his artistic vision, little detail is known about how his inclination toward unconventional topics was formed. By revisiting primary and secondary sources about MacMillan's life and career, and by considering them within the context of postwar British dance and drama, this article explores how this tendency toward dramatic subject matter progressively took shape during his first years as a choreographer and purposely crystalized in 1960 with his ballet *The Invitation*.

KEYWORDS

Kenneth MacMillan, Royal Ballet, postwar British ballet and drama, Angry Young Men, *Look Back in Anger*, *The Invitation*.

December 30, 1960, was an evening of ballet and celebration at London's Royal Opera House. It was the bicentenary of the death of dancer and choreographer John Weaver (1673–1760), and the occasion received special attention in the performance's program notes. An article by Philip J. S. Richardson, founding editor of *Dancing Times*, outlined the merits of "the father of British ballet," and highlighted how his narrative ballet *The Loves of Mars and Venus* (1717) had inaugurated a tradition in England that was still active nearly 250 years later.¹ Surprisingly, the